

Energy Measures

Tailored measures supporting energy vulnerable households

D6.6

Main communications and dissemination materials (1)

 <http://www.energymeasures.eu>

 @NRGMeasures

February 2022

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About EnergyMeasures

EnergyMeasures is working to address energy poverty in seven European countries, namely: Belgium, Bulgaria, Ireland, Netherlands, North Macedonia, Poland and the United Kingdom. The project comprises two complementary and synergistic strands of work.

The first strand involves working with energy poor households to improve their energy efficiency through a combination of low-cost measures, and changes in energy-related behaviours and practices. Recruited householders will be provided with low-cost energy measures and empowered to change their energy-related behaviours and practices through an approach that takes account of existing housing conditions and is reflective of their lived experience.

The second strand comprises working with municipalities, energy authorities, housing associations and other relevant actors to assess how current multi-level institutional contexts affect efforts to alleviate energy vulnerability in the participating countries. This knowledge will be used to develop and support the implementation of policy and practice measures which will address structural issues that combine to trap households in energy poverty.

Through this work the project contributes to reducing participants' vulnerability to energy poverty, while at the same time cutting household energy consumption and associated GHG emissions.

For more information see <http://www.energymeasures.eu>

Description of the deliverable and its purpose

This deliverable provides an overview of the Communication (T6.1) and Dissemination (T6.2) activities of the EnergyMeasures project that have been completed over the past 18 months. Both tasks (supplemented by a workshop series (T6.3), which has not yet started at the present time) together comprise WP6, spanning the entire duration of the project. A sequel to this deliverable (D6.7), which will include the Communication and Dissemination activities of the second half of the project, is scheduled for month 36.

The purpose of this deliverable, in the form of a report, is to summarize the progress of WP6 at the halfway point of the project period and to document the efforts made.

Glossary

WP	Work Package
DoA	Description of Action
OKP	Oikoplus GmbH
UCC	University College Cork

1. Description of completed tasks

1.1. Communicating EnergyMeasures

The objectives of the Work Package as well as the essential steps to achieve these objectives are specified in the DoA:

“The objective of this work package is to maximise the impact of EnergyMEASURES, by achieving the maximum awareness of the project and its results among stakeholders in fuel poverty and consumer behaviour change, and disseminating the best practice methods for engagement of energy poor citizens developed during the project. The WP includes two main areas of work:

- *Communications plan to ensure the widest possible awareness of the project its outputs;*
- *Dissemination strategy to ensure the outputs and lessons from the project contribute to change in policy and practices in tackling energy poverty.” (DoA, p.25)*

A detailed description of the selected communication approach is provided in the Communication Plan (D6.2) submitted in Project Month 3 (November 2020). At the beginning of the project, the communicative task was to provide the project with a visual identity that was as distinctive as possible. In addition, some conceptual work was done with the aim of giving the project communication a strategic framework (see D6.2: 5.2).

1.1.1. Joint development of the communication strategy

Since the beginning of the project, OKP as lead beneficiary of WP6 has pursued the strategy to involve the other partner organizations in the EnergyMeasures project as actively as possible in the project communication and dissemination. In particular, since the main project activities, such as household engagement, were to take place in very specific, national settings, making it difficult to reach certain parts of the target groups, especially households, through general project communication. Individual communication approaches and strategies for the individual countries involved in the project appeared to be absolutely necessary from the very beginning.

OKP has therefore taken on the role of a provider of communication materials, providing the other consortium partners with materials for communication, each of which can be translated into national languages and adapted to local conditions and communication requirements.

The main target groups for project communication were identified at an early stage of the project. On the one hand: households and on the other: administrators of housing. A clear set of key messages was defined for both target groups, each of which was to be conveyed through the following project communication (see D6.2: 5.6).

<p>Basic Key Messages in addressing households:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Anyone can implement low cost measures • These are the necessary low-cost measures • Energy behaviour change is easy and affordable 	<p>Basic Key Messages in addressing administrators of housing:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enabling energy behaviour change is an asset • Saving energy supports cleaner lifestyles • Behavioural change need stimulus and advertisement
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The main channels of project communication were identified as: 1) Project Website (D6.2: 5.7.1); 2) Social Media (D6.2: 5.7.2), Newsletter (D6.2: 5.7.3).

In the Communication Plan it was already stated that although project communication can be planned at the beginning of a project, it has to be flexible in order to be successful (see D6.2: 6). This also proved to be the case, so that project communication has since developed in a lively and diverse manner.

In the process, all project partners were involved as actively as possible. Not only by asking them at every stage for wishes, feedback and constructive criticism on the communication tools developed by OKP, but also by involving them in the development of project communication in the form of interactive workshops.

On February 11, 2021 (project month 6), a Key Message Development Workshop developed and facilitated by OKP was held with all project partners. Another Communication & Dissemination Workshop based on this was held on April 15, 2021.

1.1.2. Print Materials

Based on the collaborative workshops, a comprehensive "Comms Package #1" of templates and materials for communications to address households was provided to the consortium on April 28, 2021 (2.1). The Comms Package included templates for a General Visibility Poster (2.2); a specific Call2Action Poster to target households (2.3); the template for a roll-up display (2.4); and a template for leaflets (2.5). The materials were translated and adapted to local communication needs by OKP in collaboration with the partners during the following weeks (2.6). To make it easier for project partners to adapt the materials, the templates were made available on the browser-based design platform Canva on November 1, 2021 (project month 15).

1.1.3. Card Game

On November 22, 2021 (project month 15), a [deck of cards](#) on Energy Poverty / Energy Vulnerability was provided to OKP partners for translation into local languages (2.7). The game is based on the idea of a quartet game in which participants can playfully compare certain small-scale measures for reducing individual energy consumption in the household. The game idea: The card with the more effective measure beats the card of the opponent with the lower efficiency. The partners are currently still working on the translations.

1.1.4. Project Website

In addition to these materials, which primarily serve to communicate the project partners with the target group of households, the website has been the central channel for EnergyMeasures communication since the start of the project. The basic functionality as well as the technical setup of the website are described in D6.4 Project Website, submitted in October 2020 (project month 2). The project website contains a detailed [project work plan](#) and a general [project description](#), a download section with all previous [project outputs](#) and a [news section](#) where blog posts are published regularly. As of today, 17 articles have been published.

1.1.5. National Landing Pages

During the summer months of 2021, it became apparent that it was proving difficult for most of the EnergyMeasures partners to attract households to participate in the project. The various reasons for this will not be discussed in detail here. Therefore, from a communications perspective, OKP and the UCC developed a plan to put individual landing pages online for each project location that would make it easier to recruit households to the project. Since August 2021 (project month 12), OKP has implemented a total of seven such landing pages in the respective national languages. Interested households can use the landing pages to contact the national project partners directly. The national landing pages are accessible via a clickable map on the project website's front page.

Country	Project Location	Landing Page URL
BE	Turnhot	https://energymeasures.eu/belgium/
IE	Cork	https://energymeasures.eu/cork/
IE	Dublin	https://energymeasures.eu/dublin/
NL	Eindhoven	https://energymeasures.eu/eindhoven/
PL	Bielsko-Biala	https://energymeasures.eu/poland/
MK	Skopje	https://energymeasures.eu/north-macedonia/
BG	Burgas/Gabrovo	https://energymeasures.eu/bulgaria/
UK	Outer Hebrides	https://energymeasures.eu/uk/

1.1.6. Social Media Channels

In addition to the print materials, the website and national landing pages, OKP has operated social media channels on [Instagram](#) (67 postings so far), [Facebook](#) (67 postings so far) and [Twitter](#) (780 Tweets so far) for the EnergyMeasures project since the start of the project, where editorial content is regularly distributed. The Twitter channel was already operated by UCC before the project began and has since been curated by both OKP and UCC. It serves in particular for networking with peer projects. Find examples of EnergyMeasures Social Media content under section 2.8)

1.1.7. Videos

In December 2021 (project month 16), a [project video](#) was created that can be used supportively in Household Engagement by partners to promote the project. The translation and subtitling of the video is still in progress, as of today.

During the first ever physical partner meeting, in December 2021 in Dublin (project month 16), OKP also produced an [interview video](#) with several of the project stakeholders in attendance. The release of short snippet videos based on it via the project's social media channels is envisaged for the next weeks (project month 19 onwards).

1.1.8. Newsletter

A periodic [EnergyMeasures Newsletter](#) has been published in December 2021 (project month 16) (2.9).

1.1.9 Communication through Partner's Channels

In the course of the first half of the project, it became apparent that the intention to use existing channels of the project partners to promote household engagement seemed to be a suitable means of reaching a

larger number of households as quickly as possible and through established communication channels. To this end, the project's national implementing partners used different, individual communication formats in their home regions (2.10).

1.2. List of Communication and Dissemination Activities

- Press release on project launch
- Communication Plan (D6.2)
- Roll-up banner template
- Presentation templates
- Partner Portraits
- Partner Quotes
- Social Media Work and Blog entries based on D1.1 and D1.2(Twitter and Instagram Fleets)
- CANVA graphics based on D1.1 and D1.2
- Preparation of implementation plans for Comms work
- D 4.2 Project website
- Web-development
- Website domain registration
- Description on EM website
- Basic website infrastructure and development
- Website frontend development and landing page
- Vectorization project flow graphics
- Layout graphics
- Animation graphics
- Page Fixes; Updates; Plug-in installations & maintenance
- Web Security Certificates
- Household engagement text
- Video 'The Basic Value Proposition of EnergyMeasures Towards Householders'
- Roll-up display + template (Comms package no 1)
- Project leaflet (template + North Macedonia) (Comms package no 1)
- General visibility poster (Comms package no 1)
- Leaflet (2) + template (Comms package no 1)
- Flyer/ Cork and Dublin version (Comms package no 1)
- Poster/ Cork and Dublin (Comms package no 1)
- Call 2 action poster/ template, Cork and Dublin (Comms package no 1)
- Household engagement templates Canva + manual
- Promotion Video + text for translations
- Newsletter
- Energy Saving Card game + template + text for translation
- Social Media presence (FB, Instagram, Twitter)
- Blog entries published on website

2. Compendium of Materials

2.1. Comms Package #1 email sent to consortium

2.2. General Visibility Poster

2.3. Call2Action Poster

**ARE YOU
STRUGGLING
TO HEAT
YOUR
HOME?**

The EnergyMeasures project can provide:

- Energy savings report for your home
- Small energy saving devices & measures
- Personalised advice on energy behaviours
- Ongoing support and advice

Join the EnergyMeasures project for free!

 EnergyMeasures

www.energymeasures.eu/countryX

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 894759

**ARE YOU
STRUGGLING
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YOUR
HOME?**

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- Energy savings report for your home
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- Ongoing support and advice

Join the EnergyMeasures project for free!

 EnergyMeasures

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2.4. Roll-up Display

EnergyMeasures
 UCC

**Would you like your home to be more energy efficient?
Do you want to live more comfortably and save money?**

EnergyMeasures can provide:

- Personalised energy advice
- Small scale energy measures
- Ongoing support

www.energymeasures.eu/cork

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme for Research and Innovation under Grant Agreement no 894759.

EnergyMeasures
 UCC

Are you struggling to heat your home?

EnergyMeasures can provide:

- Personalised energy advice
- Small scale energy measures
- Ongoing support

www.energymeasures.eu/cork

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Programme for Research and Innovation under Grant Agreement no 894759.

2.5. Leaflet

 EnergyMeasures

ARE YOU STRUGGLING TO HEAT YOUR HOME?

SMALL ENERGY MEASURES CAN HELP YOU LIVE MORE COMFORTABLY IN A MORE AFFORDABLE WAY!

You may be eligible to receive help from an innovative EU funded project: **EnergyMeasures**.

EnergyMeasures is working to **improve the energy efficiency of households** and can provide:

- Personalised energy advice
- Small scale energy measures
- Ongoing support

Energy Action Unit 20 Citylink Business
Park, Old Naas Road, Dublin 12, D12WV91

How does it work?

1. Go to energymeasures.eu/dublin and fill in your contact details, or call 01 4545464 and leave us a message with your name and number for a call back.
2. We will contact you to schedule an appointment and discuss how best we can help.
3. We will arrange for an energy advisor to visit you and talk about your current energy needs.
4. You will receive a report outlining recommendations and a package of small-scale measures tailored to your needs, selected from a range of options.
5. We will provide you with support periodically so that you can keep saving on energy.

Depending on the recommendations, the small measures package can include:

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2.6. Leaflet example: North Macedonia

Бонус – неколку трикови како да заштедите енергија

- ▶ Топлете вода за кафе или чај само онолку колку што ви е потребно.
- ▶ Избегнувајте ја програмата за предпереење на машината за алишта секогаш кога е можно тоа.
- ▶ Не стојте пред отворен фрижидер. Уредите за ладење трошат енергија како и оние за топлење.

За повеќе совети, за мали апарати за штедење енергија, за начините како да ги промените навиките, приклучете се бесплатно на проектот EnergyMeasures.

За проектот EnergyMeasures

EnergyMeasures е проект финансиран од Европската Комисија со цел да им помогне на домаќинствата да ја подобрат потрошувачката на енергија, преку промена на однесувањето. Проектот се спроведува во 8 европски земји од страна на 12 организации-партнери, за Македонија претставник е Хабидом Македонија.

Греењето и ладењето на домот ви претставуваат проблем?

Проектот EnergyMeasures Ви нуди решение!

Сега можете да се приклучите на проектот за енергетски мерки бесплатно.

Вклучувајќи се во проектот EnergyMeasures (Енергетски мерки) добивате:

- ▶ Извештај за заштеда на енергија во вашиот дом
- ▶ Мали уреди и мерки за заштеда на енергија
- ▶ Индивидуални совети за енергетско однесување
- ▶ Тековна поддршка

ХАБИДОМ

This project is funded by the European Union through Horizon 2020, Research and Innovation Program under grant agreement number 894759.

2.7. Card Deck

Energy Saving Quartet

Small Scale Measures

FOOD PREP

Small Scale Measures

LAUNDRY

Small Scale Measures

FOOD STORAGE

Small Scale Measures

DRAUGHTS

Small Scale Measures

HOT WATER

Small Scale Measures	
Measure	Shower head
Assessment	Quality improvement
Cost per measure	€ 30.00
Comfort level	★★★★
Reduce your shower flow rate by using a water-saving shower head.	

RADIATOR

Small Scale Measures	
Measure	Thermostatic radiator valve
Assessment	Quality improvement
Cost per measure	€ 30.00
Comfort level	★★★★
Thermostatic radiator valve allows for individual control of individual rooms from one boiler.	

LIGHTING

Small Scale Measures	
Measure	LED or CFL bulbs
Assessment	Quality improvement
Cost per measure	€ 3.50
Comfort level	★★★★
CFL's use 25-35% less energy than traditional light bulbs use. While LED's use 75% less of the energy than incandescent bulbs use.	

ELECTRIC DEVICES

Small Scale Measures	
Measure	Standby power strip
Assessment	Quality improvement
Cost per measure	€ 10.00
Comfort level	★★★★
Use a standby killer that cuts the power supply to your devices in standby mode to avoid unnecessary energy expenditure.	

COUNTRY PROFILES

THE STATE OF ENERGY POVERTY

Fuel poverty in Scotland and the island communities

In 2019 the Scottish Parliament passed the **Fuel Poverty (Targets, Definition and Strategy) Act**, which sets statutory targets for reducing fuel poverty. The overarching target is that in the year 2040, no household in Scotland is in fuel poverty and in any case no more than 5% of households are fuel poor, no more than 1% are in extreme fuel poverty.

The **Climate Change (Emissions Reduction Targets) Act 2019** sets equally ambitious targets to achieve net zero greenhouse gas emissions by 2045, with interim targets requiring a 75% reduction by 2030, and 90% by 2040. These two Acts now form the basis for action at a Scotland level on fuel poverty.

The new **Fuel Poverty Strategy**, laid before the Scottish Parliament in early November 2021 sets out the Scottish Government strategic direction to both reduce fuel poverty and emissions in collaboration, linked to the **Heat and Buildings Strategy**. Local delivery is seen as the mechanism to achieve tackling fuel poverty, but it remains to be seen the limits of funding this aspiration. There is only scant mention of behaviour change, that Scottish government fund through a national Home Energy Scotland (HES) advice service. Also, outreach capacity is minimal.

To the **Outer Hebrides** outreach services are delivered by **Tighnane House Group (THG)**. The need for such services was demonstrated in the production of the **Local Heat and Energy Efficiency Strategy (Compliance with Climate Change Act 2009)** which relied upon the work of THG to identify services, delivery and indeed the report itself.

Facts and figures about fuel poverty in Scotland and the island communities:
In Scotland 24.6% of homes (Scottish House Condition Survey 2021) are in fuel poverty with 12.4% in extreme fuel poverty. In the Highlands and Islands of Scotland, these numbers are significantly higher, with the Outer Hebrides suffering the highest levels of fuel poverty at 43% and extreme fuel poverty at 24%.

WORK PACKAGES

AN OVERVIEW OF THE CURRENT STATUS

WP 1: Planning and preparatory work

WP1 designates the planning and preparation work package for **EnergyMeasures** activities, led by **University College Cork**. This includes the successful completion of four key deliverables (D1.1, D1.2, D1.3, D1.4) that involve developing a deeper understanding of multi-stakeholder engagement in addition to assessing deliberating on the different institutional contexts in each of the partner countries, and strategies for household engagement of targeted segments of energy poor in light of the Covid-19 pandemic.

D1.1 reviews current best practices, academic discourse, and new thinking to select the most appropriate methods to identify energy poor households for the planned engagements in the project's different locations.
D1.2 provides an overview of energy-related behaviour concepts and theories, and analyses the methods used in similar initiatives to **EnergyMeasures** to propose an approach to integrate behavioural change methods with the deployment of low-cost energy measures.
D1.3 collects diverse perspectives from citizens in local communities in the focal countries about their experiences when accessing institutional support to reduce energy vulnerability.
And finally, **D1.4** provides a review of relevant EU and national policies that affect energy vulnerability in the participating countries. These deliverables will be available on the project's website shortly.

WORK PACKAGES

AN OVERVIEW OF THE CURRENT STATUS

WP 2: Household energy engagement programmes realisation

The efforts in WP2 aim to engage energy-vulnerable households in the focal countries. Project partners work with households to learn about participants' relationship with energy to help to jointly identify the necessary behaviour changes and low-cost measures that can help households address their energy vulnerability and live in a more comfortable space. These engagements not only consider the potential energy savings according to the dwelling physical attributes, but also take into account the social dimension of the lived experience of energy.

Leveraging from the outputs of WP1, each partner has developed a WP2 implementation plan to describe how energy-vulnerable households will be engaged within their individual, country-specific context. The plans include an overview of the target socio-demographic groups, the process in which these groups will be recruited, and the procedures to be adopted in the actual household visits.

The household engagements were planned to start from March 2021. However, these plans were impacted by the Covid-19 related restrictions that remained in place for the first half of 2021. As a result, the WP was restructured, and engagements started earlier this fall along with the 'opening' of society as the vaccination programme progressed and the pandemic threat lessened. So far, project partners have engaged nearly 250 households.

WORK PACKAGES

AN OVERVIEW OF THE CURRENT STATUS

WP 3: Policy and Practice Innovation

Work package 3 of the **EnergyMeasures** project is about policy and practice innovation. It aims at innovation in several ways, yet with an overarching aim (help) deliver effective energy poverty alleviation services which are also sustainable in the longer term. With the partners, work package leader **DuneWorks** will identify innovative elements in the household engagements (WP2 household energy engagement programmes realisation). But it will also engage with external innovative initiatives and stakeholders, and hold workshops to co-develop propositions and business/organisational models.

In a working session with all partners (Nov 16th), first ideas have been discussed regarding initiatives that are interesting to engage with. More working sessions will follow and for next physical project meeting a train-the-trainer workshop is planned, to support partners in conducting business modelling workshops in their respective countries. Next, **DuneWorks** will translate outcomes of all WPs into recommendations – an agenda for policy renewal, informed by citizens' and practitioners' views.

And as a special addition to WP3, **University College Cork** will set up its own maintenance and technical staff volunteer program to deliver energy poverty alleviation services in the community.

WORK PACKAGES

AN OVERVIEW OF THE CURRENT PROJECT STATUS

WP 4: Impact quantification

Does the meter reading offer enough proof?

The aim of Work Package 4 is to monitor and quantify the effects of the project. Given the multi-faceted nature of the energy poverty challenge and the objectives of the project, there are a number of different impacts to measure.

Quantitatively, we measure reduction of the energy consumption during the project to compare with an average consumption and see the effect of the applied energy measures.

We are now working with the partners to establish a uniform measurement structure, even though each partner has its own method of working, ranging from low budget energy monitoring, own CRM data system, online smart surveys to on-site meter reading.

Monitoring is not easy: data on the use of coal, wood and fuel oil is not readily available, the energy data from previous years is often blocked by the DSO and last but not least COVID-19 related restrictions are making home visits very challenging.

Qualitatively, we ask the residents whether they have been able to change their habits as a result of the tips and explanations we provide during the home visits. Reducing energy consumption is not one size fits all. During the home visits (during the span of one year) we are giving advice to households on issues such as: how to use the thermostat, how to ventilate, but also on which energy supplier to choose. Through a carefully designed interview structure, we engage in a conversation with the residents to determine together the potential areas they want to focus on, the potential effect of the proposed habit change and an evaluation on the likelihood in maintaining the chosen behaviour change measures.

Food for thought! We are measuring reduction in kWh, while at the same time energy prices are rising dramatically across Europe.

WORK PACKAGES

AN OVERVIEW OF THE CURRENT PROJECT STATUS

WP 5: Synthesis and replication

The leader of WP5 is **EcologyEnergy**, supported by **University College Cork** and all project partners, to ensure the sustainable continuation of the **EnergyMeasures** action and their replication in communities outside the project's direct scope of impact.

Even though the activities will officially start in August 2022, the key components of the work are already clear, including:

- **A deep dive into the social dimension:** intersections between energy use, socio-economic privilege and gender
- **Knowledge capture:** experience of both energy poor households, and the organisations that work to support them
- **Understanding the multi-level institutional context:** addressing EU, national, and local levels and focusing on the various policy domains relevant to energy poverty
- **Co-creating user-centred business models** focusing on the needs of the at-risk communities, governance arrangements, and policy initiatives
- **Replicating 'best practice' approaches** to engaging energy poor citizens on energy-related behavioural change

First insights from the field work, data collection and policy advocacy supported by the project are already being presented at key international events.

WORK PACKAGES

AN OVERVIEW OF THE CURRENT PROJECT STATUS

WP 6: Communication, dissemination and exploitation

The leader of the work package is **Obikplus**. Since the project started in September 2020, **Obikplus** has managed to achieve multiple results in terms of communication and dissemination elements.

Obikplus is continuously working on the creation of presentation and promotional materials to be used by the consortium. These materials include:

- Roll-up banner template
- Flyers
- Presentation templates
- Canvas graphics for social media use
- Clickable animated vector graphics
- Bi-annual newsletter
- Promotion video for household engagements
- National landing pages for all project countries

The creation of content for the blog and for social media represents an ongoing task. **Project-related content is regularly published via Twitter, Instagram and Facebook.**

PARTNER PROFILE

WHO'S BEHIND ENERGY MEASURES?

DuneWorks, Netherlands

Not too long ago, we saw huge ambitions to transform a vulnerable neighbourhood into the most sustainable neighbourhood getting stranded. Policy actors did not lack ambition, but what was missing was alignment with the residents and their needs. So, none of the zero-energy ambitions materialised – not even solar panels. Yet, instead something better happened. Based on action-research with residents, renovation propositions were developed that addressed residential needs; that offered choices; in an inclusive process, and with transparency about the sharing of costs and benefits.

DuneWorks (2016) translates between research and (policy) practice and the other way around, preferably in co-creative settings. Our area of work: sustainability transitions. We are its practice-oriented social scientists working from an environmental justice perspective (recognition of diversity; procedural and distributive justice; with attention to strengthening capabilities).

Energy poverty is increasing, energy transition policies run the risk of excluding those citizens that need support most. **EnergyMeasures** allows us to work with others to counter these trends.

Sylvia Broekers, DuneWorks

FOR INFORMATION

PLEASE VISIT

- www.energymeasures.eu
- www.facebook.com/NRGMeasures
- www.instagram.com/energymeasures
- www.twitter.com/nrgmeasures

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2.10. Examples of materials used in partners' communication channels

2.10.1. Netherlands:

The Dutch partners (DuneWorks, Het Pon & Telos, Municipality of Eindhoven) created leaflets, Instagram postings, Twitter postings, LinkedIn postings *et cetera* to advertise the project. Additionally, PowerPoint presentations have been developed for energy coach training purposes.

The image displays three communication materials for the 'Energiebox PLUS' project in Eindhoven, Netherlands. On the left is a green cardboard box filled with energy-saving items like light bulbs, a power strip, and a thermostat. In the center is a large green poster with the headline 'Bespaar ieder jaar tot €250 op je energierekening met de Energiebox PLUS' and a list of seven steps on how it works. On the right is a smaller flyer with the same headline and a section titled 'Achtergrondinformatie over de EnergieboxPLUS' which explains the project's goals and provides contact information for the energy coaches.

2.10.2. Dublin, Ireland:

- The Dublin based project partner Energy Action has distributed 10,000 leaflets among households in different districts in Dublin. Another 7,500 Leaflets have been printed and 1200 distributed to Dublin councilors for use in their areas.
- In addition, Energy Action had 40 posters printed and distributed to churches, libraries and Pharmacies.
- Two roll-up displays were used at Skylon Hotel for the Dublin Project Meeting in Dec 2021. They were also used for the first training of MABS, a large NGO Energy Action collaborates with.
- Two presentations of EnergyMeasures were held at the Commission for Regulation of Utilities (CRU). Both were conducted during workshop for Energy Suppliers and Community Stakeholders.
- Commission for the Regulation of Utilities with the support of the Electricity Association Ireland invited Energy Action to present to Energy Suppliers and the response was most favourable by 8 of the 14 Energy Suppliers.
- Social Media, mostly with LinkedIn promoting EnergyMeasures

2.10.3 Outer Hebrides, UK:

EM partner Tighean Innse Gall has produced a variety of communication materials during the first 18 months of the project. Some examples are show below.

A compilation of communications materials used to address households in the Western Isles can be accessed following this link: <https://oikoplus.faircloud.eu/s/teqBZ3eNKgwPKwy>

2.10.4 Poland

The Polish project partner PNEC has produced leaflets to address households and utilised various Social Media channels to reach out to potential project participants.

Information on the Energy advisory programme in Bielsko-Biała, Poland, was published on:

- PNEC Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/StowarzyszeniePNEC/posts/3171593459735824>
- PNEC website (about EnergyMeasures project):
 - <http://www.pnec.org.pl/pl/dzialalnosc/projektycat/5-projekty-obecnie-realizowane/833-wspieranie-gospodarstw-domowych-narazonych-na-ubostwo-energetyczne>
 - <http://www.pnec.org.pl/en/dzialalnosc/projektycat/5-projekty-obecnie-realizowane/833-wspieranie-gospodarstw-domowych-narazonych-na-ubostwo-energetyczne>
- PNEC website (about the advisory programme in Bielsko-Biała):
 - <http://www.pnec.org.pl/pl/3-aktualnoci-kat/832-w-bielsku-bialej-rusza-program-doradztwa-energetycznego-dla-mieszkanow>
 - <http://www.pnec.org.pl/en/3-aktualnoci-kat/832-w-bielsku-bialej-rusza-program-doradztwa-energetycznego-dla-mieszkanow>
 - BB Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/MiastoDobrejEnergii/posts/7838455449514015>
- Website of *Bielsko Biała protects the climate*: <https://www.miastodobrejenergii.pl/aktualnosc/program-energia-na-miare>
- Website of *Bielsko Biała Social Assistance Centre*: <https://www.mops.bielsko.pl/aktualnosc/zaproszenie-do-udzialu-w-programie-doradztwa-energetycznego-pod-nazwa-energia-na-miare>
- Website of *Housing Management Company in Bielsko-Biała*: <https://www.zgm.eu/program-energia-na-miare/>
- Website of the *Bielsko-Biała City Hall*: <https://ms.bielsko-biala.pl/aktualnosc/1/energia-na-miare-jest-dla-ciebie>
- Website of *Regional News Portal Beskidzka 24*: <https://beskidzka24.pl/bielsko-biala-doradza-jak-oszczedzac-energie/>

Chcesz mądrze korzystać z energii i chronić swój domowy budżet?

Weź bezpłatny udział w programie ENERGIA NA MIARĘ

Co otrzymasz?

- indywidualną konsultację i poradę doradcy energetycznego
- zaproszenie do udziału w konkursie z nagrodami rzeczowymi
- Energetyczny Pakiet na start

O udziale w programie decyduje kolejność zgłoszeń!
Termin ich nadsyłania upływa 14 marca 2020 r.

Zgłoszenie do programu ENERGIA NA MIARĘ - wpisz poniżej swoje dane i wrzuć formularz do urny korespondencyjnej w Urzędzie Miasta lub Radzie Osiedlowej.

1. Imię i nazwisko	
2. Adres e-mail	
3. Numer telefonu	
4. Adres zamieszkania	

Udział w programie ENERGIA NA MIARĘ krok po kroku:

- POWROT DO STRONY** – Wejdź na stronę: www.pnec.org.pl/energianamiare i wypełnij formularz lub wpisz na odwrocie swoje dane i wrzuć zgłoszenie do urny korespondencyjnej w Urzędzie Miasta lub Radzie Osiedlowej.
- ROZMOWA TELEFONICZNA** – Skontaktujemy się z Tobą, aby ustalić termin spotkania z doradcą energetycznym.
- SPOTKANIE** – Podczas spotkania z doradcą energetycznym w Twoim miejscu zamieszkania wspólnie wykonamy przegląd energetyczny Twojego domu lub mieszkania.
- OPAKOWANIE** – Otrzymasz zestaw porad energetycznych dopasowanych do Twoich potrzeb oraz Pakiet Energetyczny, który pozwoli Ci stosować proste i opłacalne rozwiązania.
- KONKURS** – Oszczędzając przez rok energię możesz wygrać nagrody rzeczowe.

Przekonaj się sam, ile zaoszczędzisz i zyskasz!

Za realizację programu odpowiada Stowarzyszenie Gmin Polska Sieć „Energie Cités”

Więcej informacji: +48 22 429 17 95 lub biuro@pnec.org.pl

Informacje na temat przetwarzania danych osobowych

1. **Administrator danych**
Administratorem danych, osób podmiotem działającym, o tym jak będą wykorzystywane Twoje dane osobowe jest Stowarzyszenie Gmin Polska Sieć „Energie Cités” z siedzibą przy ul. Szwajkowskiej 117/90, 35-026 Kraków.
Możesz skontaktować się z nami: telefonicznie: 22 429 17 95, poprzez adres e-mail: biuro@pnec.org.pl.

2. **Inspektor Ochrony Danych**
Administrator danych osobowych wnoszący Inspektora Ochrony Danych (IOD), z którym możesz się kontaktować w sprawach dotyczących Twoich danych osobowych, 2 Inspektorem możesz się skontaktować, wysyłając wiadomość na adres e-mail: biuro@pnec.org.pl.

3. **Cele przetwarzania i podstawa prawna przetwarzania**
Twoje dane przetwarzane będą na podstawie umowy w celu namierzenia z Tobą kontaktu i umówienia spotkania z przedstawicielem Stowarzyszenia, który przedstawi Ci założenia programu ENERGIA NA MIARĘ. Zgłoszenie wysyłasz w dowolnym momencie, wysyłając wiadomość na adres: biuro@pnec.org.pl. Wysłanie zgłoszenia nie wpływa na zgodność z prawem przetwarzania dokonanego na podstawie umowy przed jej wycofaniem.

4. **Okres przechowywania Twoich danych osobowych**
Twoje dane osobowe będą przetwarzane do czasu wycofania zgłoszenia lub do momentu osiągnięcia celu przetwarzania, w zależności od tego, które ze zdarzeń nastąpi jako pierwsze.

5. **Odwołanie Twoich danych**
Odwołanie Twoich danych będzie Prezydent Miasta Bielsko-Białej (Urząd Mięski w Bielsku-Białej), za pośrednictwem którego otrzymamy Twój formularz. Odwołaniem Twoich danych mogą być również inne podmioty, z których usług korzystamy w naszej działalności, np. dostawcy usług IT.

6. **Twoje prawa związane z przetwarzaniem**
Przyjmując Ci następujące prawa: prawo dostępu do danych i ich sprostowania oraz prawo do usunięcia lub ograniczenia przetwarzania.

7. **Obowiązek podania danych i konsekwencje niepodania danych**
Podanie danych jest dobrowolne, lecz niezbędne, aby możliwy było nawiązanie z Tobą kontaktu i przedstawienie założeń ww. programu.

8. **Prawo wniesienia skargi do Prezesa Urzędu Ochrony Danych Osobowych**
Jeżeli uznasz, iż przetwarzanie Twoich danych osobowych narusza przepisy Ogólnego Rozporządzenia o Ochronie Danych Osobowych (RODO), masz prawo wnieść skargę do Prezesa Urzędu Ochrony Danych Osobowych.

Ustawa z dnia 10 kwietnia 2002 r. o dostępie do informacji publicznej, w tym w ramach międzynarodowego projektu EnergyMeasures, mającego na celu wspieranie i pobudzanie świadomości energetycznej przedsiębiorstw (dotyczy: Projekt ten finansowany jest z programu Norwega 2020, realizowanego w ramach Programu Operacyjnego Inteligentny Rozwój, priorytetowa inwestycja nr 10, w ramach umowy grantu nr BNE105).